

ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS IN THE INDONESIAN PUBLIC SECTOR DURING PANDEMIC: DOES CHANGE READINESS MATTER?

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Abstract

Organizations have great challenges during the time of COVID-19 in maintaining their effectiveness and goals. A huge change in individual behavior by keeping distance to each other results in complex situations because many works have to be carried out by being away from workplaces. There are numerous factors favorable for achieving excellent performance such as leadership, employee engagement, and social responsibility becomes more interesting to discuss whether those variables are meaningful in the pandemic periodic. This research aims to analyze the influence of sustainable leadership, social responsibility on organizational effectiveness in Indonesia. We conduct a survey by distributing questionnaires using convenience sampling to selected respondents. The sample size of this research is 725 employees across organizations and public and private entities. We use the structural equation method to analyze the data collected. This research concludes that sustainable leadership, employee engagement, and social responsibility matters in explaining organizational performance variation in the emergence of COVID-19. This study also provides evidence that the degree of change readiness both low and high level, strengthens the positive effect of those independent variables on entities' performance.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Sustainable Leadership, Change Readiness.

INTRODUCTION

The outbreak of Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) has captured the world's attention since the end of 2019. The new coronavirus (SARS-CoV2) has generated an unprecedented impact in most countries of the world (Suryawan, *et al.*, 2021). Along with the increasing number of countries infected with this disease, the World Health Organization (WHO) designated COVID-19 as a global pandemic on March 11, 2020 (BBCNews, 2020). Many countries subsequently declared generalized lockdowns and quarantines as a measure to combat the spread of the disease (Abdullah *et al.*, 2020).

In Indonesia, COVID-19 has begun to become a national concern since the government announced two Indonesian citizens who tested positive for COVID-19 on March 2, 2020 (Ihsanuddin, 2020). Since then the positive cases of COVID-19 have jumped sharply to more than 17 thousand cases with more than 1,000 fatalities in mid-Mei 2020 and became to reach 671 thousand incidents by the mid of December 2020 (Worldometers.info, 2020). The rate of increase in corona cases in the country has disrupted the Indonesian economy.

The impact of the widespread cases of corona disease has also led to major changes in society. The implementation of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in various areas such as Jakarta and its surrounding cities, Bandung, Surabaya, and several other big cities, has paralyzed community activities. Since mid-March 2020, social distancing has begun to be encouraged. Office activities have shifted to work from home (WFH), educational activities migrate to school from home (SFH), closing shopping centers, and limiting activities that gather large numbers of people, have become our consumption that fills public space conversations. No doubt, this condition also has an impact on the resilience of the business world, especially in the early pandemic era.

As the pandemic becomes a daily situation in Indonesia, it is wondered how organizations such as companies, government institutions, and many others could survive. It is a big challenge for every organization to maintain its performance to provide goods and services to stakeholders. Institutions must ensure that they could achieve their goals and various targets as desired. This phenomenon has stimulated our curiosity to find out more about the factors affecting organizational effectiveness during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Many empirical findings show that organizational effectiveness may be affected by a number of factors such as leadership, employee engagement, and social responsibility. Leadership is favorable for organizational effectiveness as stated in Islam and Hossain (2019), Lee (2017), Taylor *et al* (2013), Kantabutra and Saratun (2012), Papadimitriou (2007), Rodsutti and Swierczek (2002), Wang and Satow (1994). Meanwhile, employee and organizational commitment have been investigated by BeBe and Bing (2016), Deem *et al.* (2015), Rashid *et al.* (2003) and Angle (1981) and proved to be an important factor in influencing organizational effectiveness. In addition, the social responsibility of organizations and business entities is also an important factor in determining the level of effectiveness or performance. This is as revealed by Pham & Kim (2019), Singhapakdi *et al.* (1995), and Zahra & LaTour (1987). Although many studies have been published for many years relating to organizational effectiveness and its determinant factors, not much is known about how pandemic conditions affect the organization performance variation therefore, leaving a gap in the literature that future research needs to fill.

Prior to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, organizations were operating in growing complexity. This is driven by globalization, increasingly scarce resources, social media, the use of sophisticated multimedia, and high technology. The existence of financial scandals, bankruptcies, disasters, and external pressure from various public, government and NGO interests continue to force companies to maintain their business sustainability (Smith and Sharicz, 2011). Therefore, the corona outbreak also urges organizations to adapt to environmental changes that are so fast. The Covid-19 pandemic has affected all organisations and levels in society – from individuals to institutional operations (Matli, 2020). Many entities facing rapid change in work culture, from work from office (WFO) to work from home (WFH).

Some nations have imposed various degrees of WFH policies to minimize virus contraction amongst colleagues by maintaining social distancing during COVID-19 (Wong, Cheung, & Chen, 2020). This work pattern shifting enforces numerous leaders all around the world to

adopt right policies to ensure target achievements. Therefore, employee engagement in doing excellent performance with less supervision is questionable when organizations adopt WFH system. Whether the leadership remains relevant as a determinant of organizational effectiveness during the COVID-19 pandemic is also a major research question in this study. The COVID-19 pandemic is widely acknowledged to be not only an extreme public health crisis but also causes human infections and deaths (Adnan and Hasan, 2021). Thus, this situation imposes senses of helping each other and enhances social awareness not only among colleagues but also people surrounded. It is also quite interesting to take social responsibility into account when observing organizational effectiveness in the time of COVID-19. On the other hand, readiness to change is an important variable in accelerating organizational adaptation (Mathew *et al.*, 2014) and Caliskan & Isik (2016). This is understandable considering that we will both face the transition situation towards the pandemic period. Level of change readiness is put forward to strengthen or weaken leadership and other factors in affecting organization performance during the COVID-19 outbreak.

In our study, we use sustainable leadership as our main concern. There is an awareness that a company or organization cannot survive in the long term, except for those who care about the people who work in the organization and their social and physical environment, the concept of sustainable leadership emerges. This leadership concept emphasizes more on long-term prosperity. The role of the leader is not only to promote output, but also to ensure that these results must be produced continuously (Lee, 2017). Thus, in particular, this research is expected to provide academic and practical contributions related to the favourability of sustainable leadership in promoting organizational effectiveness. Other contributions provided by this study is how does the level of change readiness become essential for organizations to adapt with pandemic situation in achieving entity's goals.

Concept of Organizational Effectiveness

There are various models of organizational effectiveness, each representing a different perspective. Organizational effectiveness is the extent to which the organization achieves its goals or objectives. This is as described in the goal model (Etzioni, 1964; Georgopoulos and Tannenbaum, 1957; Hall, 1978; Price, 1972). Furthermore, organizational effectiveness is defined as the organization's ability to "acquire scarce and valuable resources". This understanding is expressed in the system resource model as in Yuchtman and Seashore (1967). The third model emphasizes organizational effectiveness in terms of the efficiency of the organization's internal processes and procedures. This narrative is known as the process model as intended by Argyris (1964), Bennis (1966), Cameron (1981) and Likert (1967). The ecological or participant satisfaction model - which is referred to as the strategic strategy model or model - defines organizational effectiveness as a way of adhering to the organization that meets the requirements of key stakeholders (Connolly *et al.*, 1980; Keeley, 1978; Miles, 1980).

All definitions of organizational effectiveness basically measure the extent to which an organization achieves its objectives – be it in terms of achieving the desired level of output, the desired level of resource utilization, the desired process efficiency in converting inputs into outputs, or the desired level of stakeholder satisfaction (Sharma and Singh, 2019).

Sustainable Leadership

While definitions of organizational effectiveness are abundant, the determinants of organizational effectiveness vary widely as well and we can find them in a number of literatures. The concept of leadership has been studied for a long time as an important part of determining organizational effectiveness. The important role of sustainable leadership in supporting organizational effectiveness and performance can be found in Suriyankietkaew and Avery (2016). They find that entities that adopt sustainable leadership practices are significantly correlated with an increase in the company's financial performance. This finding is in line with the model of Avery and Bergsteiner (2010, 2011) and the findings of other researchers, such as Bassi *et al.* (2011) and El-chaarani (2013) which state that certain sustainable leadership practices have a positive relationship with long-term financial performance in companies. Meanwhile, Lee (2017) confirmed the findings of Suriyankietkaew and Avery (2016). In fact, Lee (2017) also finds that sustainable leadership is also important in increasing the effectiveness of public sector organizations by applying three different organizational effectiveness measures.

Research conducted by Lee (2017) observes whether the sustainable leadership component has an effect on organizational effectiveness. Lee's research (2017) was conducted through observations of United States Federal government employees. This is different from the focus of previous research conducted by Suriyankietkaew and Avery (2016), where they observed small and medium-sized companies in Thailand. Nevertheless, the conclusions of Lee's research (2017) strengthen the study conducted by Suriyankietkaew and Avery (2016) that there is no component of sustainable leadership that can be ignored.

Based on above empirical findings, the first hypothesis proposed in this study is:

H1: sustainable leadership (SL) has a positive effect on organizational effectiveness.

Employee Engagement

It is widely believed that businesses currently operate in an environment full of uncertainty, especially since the corona outbreak hit the world. The most important goal of any organization is to survive and maintain in an atmosphere conducive to responding to the dynamics of the external environment. Every organizational effort is directed at increasing organizational effectiveness (Kataria *et al.*, 2013). With that in mind, most research in organizational science has focused on how to improve organizational effectiveness. Long-term effects can be achieved by a company only through the strength of employees who are willing and committed to organizational goals (Jha *et al.*, 2019).

Empirical evidence regarding the contribution of employment engagement to organizational performance and effectiveness has been presented by a number of recent studies such as Ali *et al.* (2019), Jha *et al.*, (2019), Uddin *et al.*, (2019), Ismail *et al.* (2019), Van Knippenberg *et al.* (2015), Anitha (2014), Ko and Hur (2014) Gould-Williams (2007), and Muthuswamy and White (2005). Ali *et al.* (2019) concluded that employee engagement is an important concept that accelerates employee performance in the context of employees in the textile sector in

China. While Jha *et al.* (2019) found that employees in India who are engaged in work experience positive emotions so that they contribute positively to organizational effectiveness. The findings of Jha *et al.* (2019) complement the results of previous research such as Van Knippenberg *et al.* (2015), Ko and Hur (2014) Gould-Williams (2007), and Muthuswamy and White (2005).

In light of issues of the urgency of employee involvement in predicting organizational performance and effectiveness, the second hypothesis proposed in this study is:

H2: employee engagement (EE) has a positive effect on organizational effectiveness.

Social Responsibility

Keith Davis (1960) suggested that social responsibility refers to "the decisions and actions of business actors taken for reasons at least in part outside the direct economic or technical interests of the company. The idea presupposes that corporations have not only economic and legal obligations, but also certain obligations to society that go beyond this obligation (McGuire, 1963). The discussion on social responsibility has become increasingly heated since Carol (1979) introduced the scope of social responsibility which includes four components, namely economics, law, ethics, and discretion of business performance. The four elements this basis reflects a view of social responsibility that is related to some of the definitions offered earlier but categorizes business social responsibility in a more complete way. The role of social responsibility on company performance has been studied since the 1980s. Several important studies that discuss this include Aupperle *et al.* (1985), McGuire *et al.* (1988), Waddock *et al.* (1997), Orlitzky *et al.* (2003), Aras *et al.* (2010), DiSegni *et al.* (2013), Varenova *et al.* (2014), Ahamed (2014), Alshammari (2015), Choongo (2017), Handayani *et al.* (2017), Sharabati (2018), Javid and Leven (2019), and Ikram *et al.* (2019). Most of those studies support that the social responsibility of an entity is clearly seen as contributing to the performance of entities in developed countries. McGuire *et al.* (1988) found a positive relationship between social responsibility and return on assets (ROA) in America. Meanwhile, Waddock *et al.* (1997) in his study of 469 public companies in the United States, found that corporate social responsibility is positively related to the company's financial performance in the future. In a research using meta-analysis, Orlitzky *et al.* (2003) analyzed 52 research results with 33,878 observations, finding a relationship between social responsibility and corporate performance in the United States. Meanwhile, the essential role of social responsibility in achieving their performance can also be found in several studies in developing countries (Ahamed *et al.*, 2013; Choongo, 2017; Handayani *et al.*, 2017; Sharabati, 2018, Javeed and Leven, 2019; and Ikram *et al.*, 2019). A positive relationship between corporate social responsibility and corporate performance in Malaysia was found by Ahamed *et al.* (2013). Meanwhile, a significant relationship between social responsibility and company performance in Zambia was successfully revealed by Choongo (2017). The correlation between social responsibility and corporate performance in Pakistan was found by Javeed and Leven (2017) and Ikram *et al.* (2019). Handayani *et al.* (2017) stated the influence of social responsibility on corporate performance in Indonesia and Sharabati (2018) found the important role of corporate social responsibility activities on business performance in Jordan. Similar results were previously found by Olowokudejo and

Aduloju (2011) in a study of insurance companies in Nigeria and a study by Grbac and Loncaric (2009) of the 500 largest companies in Croatia. They each suggested that social responsibility is positively related to organizational effectiveness.

Regarding to above empirical findings, we suggest that the third hypothesis in our study as follows:

H3: social responsibility has a positive effect on organizational effectiveness

Change Readiness

Furthermore, an important factor that needs to be considered by an organization in the transition period to a major change is the attitude of employees towards the change process. With the 'new normal' policy campaigned by the government, all business entities, government agencies, and non-profit organizations must prepare for a new era. The COVID-19 pandemic is expected to continue for a long time. Economic activity must be restored. This is done so that every economic actor can return to producing goods and services and turning money. Therefore, every organization is expected to quickly adapt to a new environmental atmosphere. An environment where the corona virus has always been a frightening shadow for all of us. This condition makes health protocols always an inseparable part of every community activity. Thus, a challenge has emerged in the community in the form of 'normal' activities with a new style.

Not all organizations are able to adapt to change towards a new era. To manage organizational change successfully, it is critical for every business organization to ensure that employees can change supportive behavior (Eby et al., 2000). Individuals are not passive recipients of the uncertainty and ambiguity of change (Katsaros et al., 2019). Furthermore, Beer and Nohria (2000) describe that employees' negative attitudes towards change, cynicism and unsupportive behavior towards change are the main reasons for the failure of 70 percent of early-level organizational change initiatives. The study of employee attitudes toward change uses constructs such as readiness, resistance to, commitment to, openness to, and adjustment to change (Bouckenooghe, 2010). Armenakis et al. (1993) defined change readiness as "individual beliefs, attitudes, and intentions regarding the extent to which change is required and the capacity of the organization to successfully implement those changes". Employee acceptance is very important during this process as employee attitudes are among the main issues to be considered. When planning change (Armenakis and Bedeian, 1999), and among managerial strategies for dealing with resistance (Ezerman, 1987). Change readiness in employees can affect firm performance (LeeandLee, 2018) as well as, their financial and organizational performance (Katsaros et al., 2014; Thoumrungroje and Tanasuhaj, 2007). In line with this, employee change readiness can positively affect company performance (Matthysen and Harris, 2018; Lehman et al., 2002); as well as, financial and/or organizational results of the company (Katsaros et al., 2014). Based on the above argumentations, change readiness is used as a moderating variable in the influence of the three variables (sustainable leadership, employee engagement, and social responsibility) on organizational effectiveness.

Thus, the hypotheses related to the use of change readiness as a moderating variable include the following three hypotheses:

H4: change readiness moderates the positive influence of sustainable leadership on organizational effectiveness.

H5: change readiness moderates the positive effect of employee engagement on organizational effectiveness.

H6: change readiness moderates the positive impact of social responsibility on organizational effectiveness.

Methods

This study is a quantitative research that uses a survey method. The data collected is primary data in the form of respondents' attitudes towards a number of statements. The respondents of this research are employees or employees with a minimum education level of Diploma III and have worked in government or private organizations for at least 5 years. The sample selection method used is convenience sampling. We distributed questionnaires using formal letters to several government institutions and state-owned enterprises. Various statements were developed to represent the research construct. This is because the variables studied in the form of sustainable leadership, employee engagement, change readiness and social responsibility are latent variables (cannot be observed). Therefore, an instrument in the form of several statements is used which is considered a proxy for the measurement of the variable in question. The data analysis method uses the structural equation method (SEM). Validity and reliability tests were used to ensure the data quality. The model in this study was developed from several previous studies such as Lee (2017), Suriyankietkaew & Avery. (2016), Jha et al., (2019), Charbaji (2019), BeBe and Bing (2016), Calistan and Isik (2016) and Mathew et al. (2014). The statements in the questionnaire are stated on a scale of 1-6, where the number 1 indicates the attitude of "strongly disagree" and the number 6 represents the attitude of "strongly agree". The details of the statements in the questionnaire are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Indicator on survey of organizational effectiveness

No	Variables	Type	Number of indicators	Sources	Covid-19 Indicators
1.	Organizational Effectiveness (OE)	Dependent	8 items	Lee (2017)	7 items
2.	Sustainable Leadership (SL)	Independent	10 items	Lee (2017) dan Suriyankietkaew dan Avery (2016)	5 items
3.	Employee Engagement (EE)	Independent	7 items	Jha, et al (2019)	3 items
4.	Social Responsibility (SR)	Independent	6 items	Charbaji (2009) dan BeBe and Bing (2016)	3 items
5.	Change Readiness (CR)	Moderating	11 items	Chalikan dan Isik (2016) dan Mathew et al (2014)	7 items
	Total	67 items	42 items		25 items

Source: data processed

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research data collection was carried out through the distribution of questionnaires in the form of Google form with a convenience sampling method. Questionnaires were distributed from October 16 to November 19, 2020. The media for distributing questionnaires was through the submission of formal letters to several agencies such as the Ministry of finance, the Ministry of state-owned enterprises, local governments, and private organizations. Most targeted respondents were from Java Island because this region experienced more suffering than other regions in Indonesia in terms of COVID-19 impacts. Distribution of the questionnaires through formal letters is expected to obtain a positive response considering the limitations of researchers in reaching potential respondents. The expected target respondents from distributing the questionnaire through this channel are 1,000 respondents.

Respondents who answered the questionnaire were 727 people, of which 2 were invalid because the data were incomplete. The respondent's profile is dominated by employees from government agencies as many as 566 respondents (78.1%), and the remaining 169 respondents (21.9%) are private employees (BUMN). The respondents consisted of 390 males (53.8%) and 335 females (46.2%). The proportion of respondents based on gender reflects a relatively balanced comparison. The overall respondent profile can be seen in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Respondent profile

Respondents Characteristic	Public	%	Private	%	Total	Percentage
<i>By gender</i>						
Male	292	40,3	98	13,5	390	53.8
Female	274	37,8	61	8,4	335	46.2
	566	78,1	159	21,9	725	100.00
<i>By education</i>						
Doctoral	4	0,6	2	0,3	6	0,9
Master	67	9,2	48	6,6	115	15,8
Bachelor	343	47,3	100	13,8	443	61,1
Diploma III	152	21,0	9	1,2	161	22,2
	566	78,1	159	21,9	725	100.00
<i>By employment status</i>						
Structural bureaucratic	480	66,3	-		480	66,3
Functional officers	60	8,3	-		60	8,3
Private employee (BUMN)	-		157		157	21,6
Private lecturer/teacher	7	0,9	2	0,3	9	1,2
Others	19	2,6	-		19	2,6
	566	78.1	159	21,9	725	100.00
<i>By the length of experience</i>						
More than 20 years	131	18,1	46	6,3	177	24,4
16-20 years	98	13,5	19	2,6	117	16,1
11-15 years	138	18,9	21	2,9	159	21,8
5-10 years	199	27,6	73	10,1	272	37,7
	566	78.1	159	21,9	725	100.00

Source: data processed

Research respondents as presented in Table 2 above are respondents who understand organizational problems. This can be seen from the educational background of the respondents, most of whom are undergraduate graduates (61.1%), followed by diploma III (22.2%), and master (15.8%) graduates. The respondent's work experience is also quite supportive in understanding the issues described in the questionnaire. Almost half of the respondents, namely 40.5% have more than 16 years of work experience, followed by respondents with 5-10 years of experience as much as 37.7% and 21.8% with 11-15 years of experience. Thus, in terms of capabilities, respondents who filled out the questionnaire were the right respondents to support the success of the survey.

The questionnaire data processing was carried out using the *SmartPLS 3* application. The results of the validity and reliability tests were respectively indicated by the loading factor and *cronbach's alpha* indicators. A latent variable is said to have an acceptable level of validity if the loading factor is at least 0.3 for a sample of 725. The level of reliability is acceptable if it has a Cronbach alpha of at least 0.6 (Sekaran, 2013). The results of data processing on *SmartPLS 3* show that of the 67 statements, 66 are declared valid because overall they can provide a minimum loading factor of 0.3. The five research variables have Cronbach's alpha values above 0.8. Table 3 below presents an overview of the results of validity and reliability testing.

Table 3: Summary of validity and reliability tests

Variables	Indicators			Validity (loading factor)	Reliability (Cronbach's alpha)
	Total	Valid	Not valid		
<i>Organizational effectiveness (OE)</i>	15	15	0	0,543-0,891	0,856-0,882
<i>Sustainable Leadership (SL)</i>	15	15	0	0,743-0,952	0,802-0,940
<i>Employee Engagement (EE)</i>	10	9	1	0,274-0,905	0,931
<i>Social Responsibility (SR)</i>	9	9	0	0,612-0,839	0,890
<i>Change Readiness (CR)</i>	18	18	0	0,616-0,914	0,895-0,920
Total indicators	67	66	1		

Source: data processed

Based on validity testing, almost all indicators are valid. Only one statement is invalid, namely, the measurement on the employee engagement (EE) variable because it only has a loading factor of 0.274. Employee engagement during the pandemic is more reflected in two other valid statements, namely EE.8, "*During the COVID-19 pandemic, I am still enthusiastic about doing my job*" and EE.10, "*During the COVID-19 period, I always report work to my supervisor (supervisor)*".

All valid indicators in the questionnaire have a fairly high level of reliability as well. The highest level of reliability is found in the sustainable leadership (SL) variable with work-life balance dimensions and followed by employee engagement, each of which has *cronbach's alpha* numbers 0.940 and 0.931 respectively. The lowest level of reliability is sustainable leadership (SL) on the organizational justice dimension which has a *cronbach's alpha* number of 0.802. The reliability of the indicators in the SL-related questionnaire is also supported by a

very good level of validity. It is proven that all of the SL statement items in the questionnaire (15) are declared valid.

Descriptive statistics

Table 4 presents a statistical description of the results of the questionnaires. The respondents rated the effectiveness of their organization at the level of 5,139 or generally stated "agree". Lee (2017) explains that organizational effectiveness is assessed in 3 dimensions, namely the level of satisfaction, intrinsic motivation, and macro performance. Statistically, per dimension of organizational effectiveness, it can be seen that the highest respondent's perception is related to the level of satisfaction, which is 5,200, followed by macro performance at the level of 5,129 and intrinsic motivation at 5,088. As for the level of correlation between the indicator (statement item) and its latent construct (variable), it can be seen that the statement with the OE6 code, namely "I can optimize my talents well in the organization" has the highest outer loading value of 0.891. Indicators with a high loading factor have a higher contribution to explaining the latent construct.

Table 4: Descriptive statistics

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Organizational Effectiveness (OE)	725	2,067	6,000	5,139	0.626
Sustainable Leadership (SL)	725	1,733	6.00	5,258	0.639
Employee Engagement (EE)	725	2,500	6.00	5,223	0,589
Social Responsibility (SR)	725	2,777	6.00	5,306	0,577
Change Readiness (CR)	725	2,666	6.00	5,305	0,569

Source: data processed

Regarding the COVID-19 pandemic, there are seven valid indicators related to organizational effectiveness as the dependent variable. This research makes an important contribution regarding the development of indicators that can explain the latent variables of organizational effectiveness during the corona pandemic. The statement with the code OE7 "during the COVID-19 pandemic, my talents can really be used for my organization" is an indicator that has the highest loading factor (0.859) among other COVID-19 variables. This is in line with the OE6 indicator which is the most representative indicator in measuring organizational effectiveness.

The results of further research show that of the three independent variables, social responsibility (SR) has the highest rating from the respondents. In Table 4 it is presented that on average, respondents assess the social responsibility of employees towards other employees and the surrounding community as the highest among other independent variables, namely at the level of 5.306 or above the level of "agree". Meanwhile, sustainable leadership (SL) and employee engagement (EE), respectively, have an average score of 5.258 and 5.223. In terms of the loading factor value, the indicator that has the highest loading factor for each independent variable is SL14 for sustainable leadership, EE3 for employee engagement, and SR3 for social responsibility. The SL 14 indicator, namely "leaders/senior employees show support for the work-life balance program" has a loading factor of 0.952. The statement item EE3, "I am

enthusiastic about my job” has an outer loading of 0.905. As for the SR3 statement, *“the organization minimizes environmental impacts arising from the organization's products/services”* also has a fairly high outer loading of 0.839. The three indicators above are the best indicators that represent each independent variable.

In the light of the perspective of the pandemic period, several important indicators show a strong correlation with the latent variables. It can be seen that in general the indicators related to COVID-19 can be considered to represent each of the latent variables. In general, there are 11 indicators that represent 3 independent variables and are related to the corona pandemic. The average outer loading value for sustainable leadership is 0.8828, employee engagement is 0.744 and social responsibility is 0.7243. This shows that these indicators can relatively represent sustainable leadership, employee engagement, and social responsibility variables in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. The indicator related to the COVID-19 atmosphere which has the highest outer loading is SL15, which is 0.948. The item comes from the latent variable of sustainable leadership for the work-life balance dimension, namely *“During the COVID-19 pandemic, my organizational leadership encourages employees to carry out work-life balance programs”*.

The moderating variable in this study is change readiness (CR) which has 18 valid indicators. Table 4 above informs that in general the respondents stated their agreement on readiness to change, especially in the new normal era as it is today. This can be seen, the average value of this variable is 5.306 which means it is above the level of "agree". The highest loading factor for the CR indicator is CR10 which states *“A change project to solve current problems, will provide a lot of goodness”* and is worth 0.914. The results of this research indicate that changes made today must be accompanied by a spirit of optimism to obtain good in the future. This indicator is the measure that best represents the latent variable “readiness to change”. The indicators related to the COVID-19 pandemic consist of 7 statement items, each of which has an outer loading above 0.7. This condition implies that technology adoption is a necessity that must be done during the pandemic.

Data processing with the SEM method does not require a complete classical assumption test, but only multicollinearity testing. Based on collinearity testing with the SmartPLS 3 application, information is obtained that the three independent variables each have a variance inflation factor below 10. This means that the correlation variables between SL, EE, and SR are still acceptable. The R-squared for this study is 0.779. This means that the independent variable is able to explain the dynamics of organizational effectiveness (EO) and has an impact of 77.9%. While the rest, 22.1% is explained by other variables outside this research model. More details about the analysis of the relationship between variables are presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Path Diagram of Full Sample Hypothesis Testing Output Results

Moderating test

Testing the hypothesis with a test of significance (Hair et al., 2006) using the AMOS 6 program. Specifically for the hypothesis related to the moderating variable in this study, it will be tested with multigroup SEM. Multigroup analysis was used to detect and evaluate the moderating role of the change readiness variable on the effect of sustainable leadership, employee engagement and social responsibility on organizational effectiveness. The multigroup analysis procedure in the SEM context includes dividing the sample into groups, in this study, namely ‘low’ and ‘high’ on the perception of the change readiness variable, then making a structural equation model of constrained parameters and non-constrained parameters.

The constrained parameter structural equation model assumes that there is no difference between the moderating variables in moderating the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The unconstrained parameter structural equation model assumes that there are differences between the moderating variables in moderating the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

The calculated chi-square value is greater than the chi square (X²) table, so the parameter structural equation model is not constrained to be accepted, meaning that there are differences between the hypothesized moderating variables in moderating the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable and further analysis can be carried out.

The results of the test of whether change readiness is able to become a moderating variable is shown by the Chi-Square value of 2353,795 with a prob value of 0.000 < 0.05, it is concluded that there are differences between the hypothesized moderating variables in moderating the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable and further analysis can be carried out.

Hypothesis test

This study aims to observe the influence of sustainable leadership, employee engagement, and social responsibility on organizational effectiveness in the time of COVID-19. Table 5 below is the result of hypothesis testing in this study to answer the hypothesis.

Table 5: Hypothesis test results of full sample with regression using SEM AMOS

Tests		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	Prob	Remarks
SL	→ OE	0.451	0.058	7.712	0.000	Significant
EE	→ OE	0.273	0.041	6.661	0.000	Significant
SR	→ OE	0.212	0.058	3.678	0.000	Significant

Source: Hypothesis Test Results with regression using SEM AMOS

Table 5 shows us that the sustainable leadership (SL) coefficient value is 0.451, the employee engagement (EE) coefficient is 0.273 and the social responsibility (SR) coefficient is 0.212. The three coefficient values are each significant at the 1 percent error level. These results indicate that there is a positive effect of the three independent variables on organizational effectiveness. Therefore, H1, H2, and H3 can be accepted respectively.

Figure 2 below shows the results of hypothesis testing with sub-groups divided according to respondents' perceptions regarding moderating variables (change readiness) in the 'low group' and 'high group'. These two groups represent the level of change readiness, not really ready and quite ready, respectively.

Figure 2: Path Diagram of Sub Group Hypothesis Testing Output Results

Based on the SEM analysis in Table 8 below, it can be concluded that there is a moderating effect, with the moderating variable being *change readiness* ('low group') which affects the relationship between SL and OE, EE's relationship to OE and SR's relationship to OE. Lower perception of change readiness moderate the positive effect of the variables SL, EE and SR on organizational effectiveness. Thus H4, H5 and H6 can be accepted.

Table 6: Hypothesis test results of 'low group' sample with regression using SEM AMOS

Tests		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	Prob	Remarks
SL →	OE	0.441	0.075	5.894	0.000	Significant
EE →	OE	0.302	0.051	5.914	0.000	Significant
SR →	OE	0.166	0.079	2.083	0.037	Significant

Source: Hypothesis Test Results with regression using SEM AMOS

Meanwhile, based on the results of the SEM analysis in Table 7, we may conclude that there is a moderating effect, with the moderating variable being *change readiness* ('high group') which affects the relationship of SL to OE, EE's relationship to OE and SR's relationship to OE.

Therefore, it can be explained that the sample group that has a higher perception of *change readiness* moderates the effect of the variables SL, EE and SR on organizational effectiveness. In other words, H4, H5 and H6 are acceptable in this study.

Table 7: Hypothesis test results of ‘high group’ sample with regression using SEM AMOS

Tests		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	Prob	Remarks	
SL	→	OE	0.514	0.113	4.542	0.000	Significant
EE	→	OE	0.178	0.075	2.384	0.017	Significant
SR	→	OE	0.336	0.098	3.411	0.000	Significant

Source: Hypothesis Test Results with regression using SEM AMOS

Sustainable Leadership and COVID-19

Leadership has a strong influence on an organization in realizing its vision and mission. In the context of sustainable leadership (SL), there are 5 important dimensions that need to be observed, namely cohesive diversity, organizational justice, employee development, progress orientation, and work-life balance (Lee, 2017). In this study, each dimension of sustainable leadership is measured by 3 indicators. Indicators of organizational justice and progress orientation each have a high average score from the respondents, namely 5.3327 and 5.2719 (above the 'agree' criteria). The organizational justice dimension reflects the concern of the organization to uphold the principle of fairness and stay away from discriminatory attitudes. This policy is of course very conducive in bringing the organization to carry out its mission. The most prominent indicator in organizational justice is SL5, “Personnel practices, such as discrimination, are not allowed in my organization” which was rated on average at 5.5531 by the respondents. This means that the respondents agreed on the need to stay away from acts of discrimination. On the other hand, the dimension of progress orientation is also an important indicator in sustainable leadership. A good organization has an orientation to always advance its business. The most prominent indicator is SL12, “Organizational leadership evaluates organizational performance during the COVID-19 pandemic”, obtaining an average score of 5.3591 from the respondents. This shows that respondents have a perception of the importance of evaluating performance during the pandemic.

The important role of leadership in realizing organizational effectiveness is in line with research conducted by Lee (2017). In his research on the public sector in the United States, Lee (2017) found that the five elements of sustainable leadership have a positive impact on organizational effectiveness at the federal government level. This similar research result is also caused by the characteristics of the respondents. Most of the respondents in this study (78.1%) came from the government sector, while Lee (2017) research respondents were all employees of the central (federal) government. However, the results of this study are slightly different from the findings of Rahmawati et al. (2016) and research by Islam and Hossain (2019). Rahmawati et al. (2016) when examining the effectiveness of government organizations (SKPD) in South Sulawesi Province did not find a positive influence of leadership on organizational performance. Likewise, Islam and Hossain (2019) also did not find a positive

relationship between leadership and effective organization in training institutions in Bangladesh. This difference in results is partly due to differences in respondent characteristics that may differ between central civil servants, regional government civil servants, and the characteristics of respondents in Bangladesh. In addition, research by Rahmawati et al. (2016) and Islam and Hossain (2019) only use leadership variables in general, not sustainable leadership variables as developed in this research. Further research can be conducted to see whether indicators of sustainable leadership can be applied to local government organizations and training organizations in Indonesia in assessing the determinants of organizational effectiveness.

In the context of sustainable leadership during a pandemic, this study found that all five indicators that reflect COVID-19 are valid indicators. The five indicators represent 5 dimensions of sustainable leadership, namely cohesive diversity, organizational justice, employee development, progress orientation, and work-life balance. Respondents considered that the dimension of progress orientation plays an important role in achieving an effective organization during the pandemic. It is evident that the respondents' highest assessment of the indicators of sustainable leadership during the pandemic is the SL12 indicator, namely "Organizational leaders evaluate organizational performance during the COVID-19 pandemic" with an average value of 5.3591.

Employee Engagement and COVID-19

Kahn (1992) argues that voluntary employee involvement can encourage engagement with work and other people, personal presence, and full active role driven by a conducive work environment. Employees who have high morale have a positive effect on organizational performance. Engaged employees have an influence on efforts to work voluntarily, in the form of extra time, brain power, and energy (Kennedy & Daim, 2010). This study revealed that respondents gave a fairly high assessment of employee engagement, which was an average of 5.222 (above the level of "agree"). Nine out of ten indicators in this variable are declared valid based on loading factor analysis. In general, respondents from government organizations gave an average rating of better (5.2662) than the private sector (4.9903) related to employee engagement variables.

An important indicator in this variable is EE10, "During the COVID-19 period, I always report my work to my supervisor (supervisor)" which is rated on average at 5.4627 by respondents. Regarding this indicator, respondents from the government organization also gave a relatively better rating (5.5045) compared to private organizations (5.2338). This implies that employees' engagement with their direct supervisors is stronger in government agencies than in private entities. The principle of inherent supervision that has always been applied in government offices has in fact formed a good culture in the world of bureaucracy. Civil servants have an obligation to always report work to their direct superiors because there is also an employee performance assessment in the form of a Job Implementation Assessment List (DP3). The DP3 instrument is considered effective for ensuring employee performance at a good level because DP3 is one of the requirements for both promotion and promotion opportunities. Statistically, respondents from government agencies are dominated by structural employees (84.63%). The

respondent's profile also confirms the existence of a hierarchical reporting system in stages from subordinates to superiors among these bureaucrats.

This important role of employee engagement on organizational performance and effectiveness confirms previous empirical studies such as Jha et al., (2019) and Ali et al. (2019). The research of Jha et al. (2019) was conducted on employees of information technology companies in India. They found the important role of employee engagement in mediating the relationship between employee voice and organizational effectiveness. Meanwhile, Ali et al. (2019) revealed that employee engagement is an important element in accelerating employee performance at textile companies in China. This study also supports the findings of Slatten & Mehmetoglu (2011) regarding the role of employee engagement as the key to business success. Several empirical studies have also shown that employee engagement can improve employee performance, profitability, customer satisfaction, employee retention and organizational success (Bates, 2004; Baumruk, 2004; Richman, 2006). Thus, this study provides additional contributions regarding empirical evidence of the positive impact of employee engagement on organizational performance and effectiveness.

In the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, the next valid indicator that is important in measuring employee engagement is EE8, "During the COVID-19 pandemic, I am still enthusiastic about doing my job". The average assessment of respondents on these two indicators is 5.3411, respectively. According to respondents, government organizations have an average perception value of 5.3867 and that of the private sector is 5.0922. This condition indicates that the respondents have various responses to completing work remotely. Government employees remain enthusiastic about work, possibly because there is no reduction in monthly incentives. This is different from private employees who may experience a decrease in income while working from home. Differences in internet accessibility and supporting equipment may be one of the reasons why there are respondents who do not like WFH. Nevertheless, the respondent's preference level for employee engagement indicators during the corona pandemic is quite good because it is still at 5 and above ("agree" and "strongly agree"). This preference for working remotely will greatly determine how prepared respondents are to change and adapt to the environment.

Social Responsibility and COVID-19

Social responsibility is one of the important elements in maintaining the sustainability of the organization, especially if the organization is a private sector that tends to pursue profit. Environmental, economic, and social practices are practices that are commonly encountered by every organization. However, in this study the statements developed in the questionnaire tended to be non-economic issues. There are 9 indicators that are declared valid to represent social responsibility variables, of which 3 indicators reflect social responsibility practices in the pandemic era. In general, respondents rated their organizational social responsibility at a very good level, namely an average of 5.3063 (above the level of "agree"). Respondents of government employees rated social responsibility in their organization relatively higher (5.3417) than respondents from the private sector (5.1023). This condition indicates that the government sector's concern for social responsibility issues tends to be better than the private

sector. This condition is slightly contrary to the view of the private sector so far which is often associated with organizations that seek to maintain their business continuity through social activities. This phenomenon is quite interesting to observe considering that most of the respondents from the private sector are from SOEs. The issue of social responsibility should be an important issue for SOEs to be able to maintain their business continuity in order to compete with the private sector.

The social responsibility indicator (SR) that has the highest score (5.6256) is SR4, which is “*Ethical values are important to me*”. Bureaucratic respondents have a relatively higher rating (5.6453) compared to respondents from private organizations (5.4674). This assessment provides a signal that ethical values in government organizations tend to be better than private organizations. This fact could be due to the very strong ethical values in the world of bureaucracy.

On the other hand, the most important SR indicator related to the pandemic period is SR7, namely “*My organization pays attention to health protocols for its employees during the COVID-19 pandemic*” with an average score of 5.4507. Bureaucratic respondents gave a better rating (5.4659) than private respondents (5.3037). However, it can be concluded that both government employees and private employees view health protocols as important to implement during the pandemic.

This study found that social responsibility (SR) has a positive effect on organizational effectiveness. Although the respondents are dominated by government employees, the issue of social responsibility remains relevant in explaining organizational dynamics. People assume that government organizations are entities that carry a social mission. Especially during the pandemic, employees' concern for the surrounding environment becomes more honed. This finding confirms the results of previous research which states that there is a positive relationship and impact of social responsibility practices with organizational performance (Pham and Kim, 2019). On the other hand, the results of this study differ from those of Chang et al. (2016), Athapaththu and Karunasena (2018), and Chang et al. (2018), where they found no relationship between sustainability practices and organizational performance. This difference is partly due to the different profiles of respondents where in this research some of the respondents are government employees, while Chang et al.'s research results take respondents from the business world.

The role of change readiness

Respondents generally gave an average rating of 5.3058 for the change readiness factor. This value is the second highest average number after the social responsibility variable. The most important indicators in this variable are CR16 (5.4868) and CR18 (5.5455). These two indicators are indicators of adaptation to change during the pandemic era and are related to the use of technology. The CR16 indicator, “*Organizations have utilized information technology for employee attendance during the COVID-19 pandemic*” indicates that most organizations have utilized technology for monitoring employee attendance. The CR18 indicator, “*The organization has utilized information technology to hold online meetings during the COVID-*

19 pandemic” indicates that the organization has used technology a lot for virtual meetings. These two conditions illustrate that in general, the government and private organizations that are the objects of this research are ready to adapt to change.

The change readiness (CR) variable moderates the positive influence of all independent variables on organizational effectiveness, both for groups of respondents who assess change readiness at a low level and groups of respondents who assess change readiness at a high level. Statistically, the coefficient of the effect of sustainable leadership on the group with a higher change readiness (0.514) gives a higher impact on organizational effectiveness compared to the group of respondents with a lower level of readiness (0.441). The impact of this readiness to change will be more pronounced in organizations led by someone who carries out the principles of sustainable leadership well. The leadership factor is again proven to be an important factor for realizing organizational effectiveness. Likewise, the social responsibility factor in organizations that have a higher level of readiness to change (0.336) will have a stronger impact on organizational effectiveness than organizations with a lower level of readiness to change (0.166). This shows that organizations that are more ready to change will provide a positive push for social responsibility in boosting organizational performance. Furthermore, employee engagement has a more pronounced impact on organizations with a low level of change readiness (0.302) compared to entities that are relatively more ready to change (0.178). This condition provides evidence that the spirit to change is needed to encourage employee engagement in supporting the achievement of organizational goals.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to analyse the factors that affect organizational effectiveness, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. Research using questionnaire data reveals that sustainable leadership (SL), employee engagement (EE), and social responsibility (SR) have a positive impact on the organization.

The change readiness variable has been shown to moderate the positive influence of all independent variables on organizational effectiveness. This finding provides evidence that an organization will be more effective if it is supported by good leadership, employee engagement, and social responsibility that is supported by change readiness from its employees.

The research implication for policy makers is to reconsider the impact of large-scale social restrictions in order to prevent the spread of COVID-19. The effectiveness of the organization is greatly affected by the corona pandemic. The practical implication is that government and private organizations need to support efforts to increase the sustainable leadership capacity of their managers. In addition, the work spirit of its employees needs to be nurtured so that they can perform well during the pandemic. Each organization is expected to be able to provide awareness to its employees to be ready to adapt to changes, especially to intensify the use of information technology during the pandemic era.

This study has several limitations. The research respondents were only 725 and most of them work in Java. The expansion of the number of respondents in terms of number and location of

work will provide an overview of possible different results. The research variable has not accommodated the principles of good governance which have been empirically proven to have an impact on organizational performance. The composition of respondents, which are mostly civil servants, cannot fully reflect the effectiveness of the organization as a whole.

Further research is expected to increase the number of respondents from the private sector. These respondents have different characteristics than the respondents in this research. The use of mediating variables for the role of external and internal auditors is expected to enrich the discussion of future research.

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